

Comparative Randomised Double Blinded Study to Evaluate the Effectiveness and Safety of Tranexamic Acid in Preventing Postpartum Haemorrhage against Placebo in Women Undergoing Caesarean Section

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Abstract:

Objective: To assess the effectiveness of tranexamic acid (TXA) compared to placebo in reducing postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) among women undergoing caesarean section.

Methods: This double-blind randomized controlled trial enrolled 200 patients undergoing caesarean section. The TXA group received 1 gram of tranexamic acid intravenously before skin incision, while the placebo group received saline. Blood loss, need for additional medications, blood transfusions, and hemoglobin levels were compared between groups.

Results: TXA significantly reduced total blood loss up to 2 hours postpartum (346.7 ml vs. 385.85 ml, $p=0.001$) and the incidence of blood loss exceeding 500 ml (3% vs. 12%, $p=0.02$). There was no significant difference in the need for additional uterotonics but fewer patients in the TXA group required blood transfusions (3% vs. 17%, $p=0.01$). TXA patients also maintained higher post-operative hemoglobin and hematocrit levels.

Conclusion: TXA effectively reduces blood loss and the need for blood transfusions after caesarean section, improving patient outcomes and safety.

Keywords: Postpartum hemorrhage (PPH), Tranexamic acid (TXA), Caesarean section, Blood loss, Blood transfusion, Hemoglobin, Hematocrit.

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Introduction

Maternal mortality remains a significant global health challenge, with the Sustainable Development Goal 3.1 aiming to reduce the global maternal mortality ratio (MMR) to fewer than 70 per 100,000 live births by 2030. Despite notable progress, MMR remains alarmingly high in certain regions, particularly in South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa, where approximately 86% of all maternal deaths occurred in 2017 [1]. The primary causes of maternal morbidity and mortality globally—sepsis, hypertensive disorders, and maternal bleeding—are largely preventable or curable. Improving maternal health not only saves lives but also yields significant socioeconomic benefits and enhances the overall health system [2].

In India, efforts to reduce maternal mortality have shown promising results, with the national Sample Registration System (SRS) reporting a MMR of 97

per 100,000 live births in 2017-18, indicating a significant decline. Initiatives like the Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY) and the Labor Room Quality Improvement Initiative (LaQshya) have contributed to this progress. However, India still accounted for 12% of global maternal deaths in 2017, highlighting the need for continued efforts. Hemorrhage remains the leading cause of maternal deaths in India, underscoring the importance of effective management strategies [3].

Postpartum hemorrhage (PPH), defined as blood loss exceeding 500 milliliters after vaginal delivery or 1,000 milliliters during a caesarean section, is a major contributor to maternal morbidity and mortality. PPH can lead to severe complications, including infections, severe anemia, and the need for blood transfusions and hospital admissions. Notably, most PPH cases occur unexpectedly and

affect women without pre-existing risk factors [4]. A study in rural India reported a PPH prevalence of 9.2% among 1,620 women, with no significant differences in sociodemographic or maternal characteristics between those with and without PPH.

The increasing prevalence of caesarean sections (C-sections) has further exacerbated the challenge of managing PPH, especially in high-risk anemic populations [5]. Effective strategies to reduce blood loss during lower-segment caesarean sections (LSCSs) are crucial for minimizing bleeding-related maternal mortality.

A well-equipped healthcare system plays a pivotal role in improving maternal health outcomes by preventing and promptly treating PPH, adhering to a continuum of care that includes uterotonics, temporizing measures, and emergency surgeries when necessary [6].

Tranexamic acid (TXA), an antifibrinolytic drug, has been shown to significantly reduce bleeding during surgery and trauma. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends the early use of intravenous TXA (within 3 hours of birth) as part of the standard treatment for clinically diagnosed PPH.

Despite this, the Indian guidelines on PPH therapy have not been updated to reflect the WHO's recommendations, and TXA is not yet standard in government programs like the DAKSHATA programmed, which aims to improve maternal and newborn care. Given this context, the present study aims to assess the effectiveness of tranexamic acid in preventing postpartum hemorrhage compared to a placebo in women undergoing caesarean section.

Methods

Study Setting: This hospital-based comparative double-blind randomized controlled trial was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at the Chhattisgarh Institute of Medical Sciences (CIMS), Bilaspur, Pt. Deendayal Upadhyay Memorial Health Science & Ayush University of Raipur.

Type of Study: Comparative Double-Blind Randomized Controlled Trial.

Study Duration: The study was conducted from January 2023 to February 2024.

Sampling and Sample Size: Two hundred consecutive patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria were included in the study after obtaining written informed consent.

Minimum Sample Size Determination: For an equivalent design, the following formula is applicable in randomized controlled trials

(RCTs) for qualitative data:

$$N = 2 [(Z_{1-\alpha/2} + Z_{1-\beta})/\delta]^2 \times P(1-P)$$

Where:

- N = Minimum sample size per group
- P = Prevalence rate (assumed as 50% or 0.50)
- α = Level of significance, taken as 95%
- $(1-\beta)$ = Power of the test = 80%
- δ = The real difference between two treatments or clinical acceptance margin = 10% (assumed as 0.10)
- $Z_{1-\alpha/2}$ = Standard normal variable = 1.96
- $Z_{1-\beta}$ = 0.845

Calculating the sample size:

$$N = 2(1.96 + 0.845/0.10)^2 \times 0.50 \times 0.50$$

$$N = 2 \times (2.805/0.10)^2 \times 0.50 \times 0.50$$

$$N = 196.44$$

Hence, the minimum total sample required was rounded to 200 (100 in each group).

Study Population

Antenatal women with term pregnancy undergoing caesarean section in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at CIMS, Bilaspur.

Inclusion Criteria

- Gestation age between >37 weeks and <42 weeks
- Age >18 years and <35 years
- Alive fetus
- Hemoglobin >9 gm% in recent third-trimester reports
- Subject receiving spinal anesthesia for caesarean section
- Women with high-risk pregnancies (e.g., PIH, polyhydramnios, oligohydramnios, fetal distress, chorioamnionitis, history of caesarean section or PPH, twin pregnancy, prolonged and obstructed labor, prolonged induction, APH)

Exclusion Criteria

- Subjects with medical disorders such as renal disease, heart disease, or liver disease complicating pregnancy
- Known case of coagulation disorders
- Intrauterine fetal death
- Women on anticoagulant therapy during the week before delivery
- History of seizures
- Allergy to tranexamic acid
- Subject receiving general anesthesia for caesarean section

Method of Data Collection

Patients admitted to the ward in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at CIMS, Bilaspur during the study period were considered for inclusion

based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Data was collected through a pre-tested and structured proforma for each patient, which included detailed history, clinical examination, and laboratory investigations.

Study Tools

Pre-structured Proforma

Methodology

1. Information was collected through a pre-tested and structured proforma for each patient. Qualifying patients underwent detailed history, clinical examination, and laboratory investigations. Patient's clinical history and examination findings were recorded prospectively.
2. After obtaining informed consent from the participants, they were divided into two groups by randomization.
3. The included women were randomly placed into two groups: the trial group (Group A) and the placebo group (Group B). Each group contained 100 patients. Women in the trial group were administered 1 gm of tranexamic acid (diluted in 10 ml of 0.9% normal saline) intravenously, 20 minutes prior to the skin incision. Women in the placebo group were given an intravenous dose of 10 ml of 0.9% normal saline.

Randomization and Blinding Technique: Participants were allotted to either of the two groups by block randomization using sealed envelopes grouped in blocks. Participants picked one of the sealed envelopes of a block, which were opened sequentially.

Allocation Concealment: Participants were offered to pick one of the sealed envelopes of a block, which were opened sequentially.

Procedure: Soon after clamping the umbilical cord, all the women were administered an infusion of 20 IU of diluted oxytocin over three hours as per hospital protocol. The requirement for additional uterotonic drugs and need for blood transfusion during or within 24 hours after the caesarean section was noted. The total amount of intraoperative and postoperative blood loss was recorded. Baseline variables, preoperative and postoperative (48 hours after surgery) hemoglobin and hematocrit values were recorded.

Measurement of Blood Loss

Intraoperative Blood Loss:

1. Blood absorbed by soaked surgical mops (dry weight + wet weight)
2. Blood absorbed by perineal sheets, surgical drapes, and pads during vaginal toileting (dry weight + wet weight)
3. Blood collected in suction container

Postoperative Blood Loss:

1. Blood absorbed by gynecology pads for three hours postoperatively (dry weight + wet weight)
2. One mg weight was taken as equivalent to 1 ml of blood.

Laboratory Investigations

- Complete Blood Count (Hb)
- ESR
- Urine output
- Vital statistics like blood pressure, heart rate, respiratory rate, temperature, and SpO₂

If PPH or any adverse event occurred at any point during the study, standardized management was provided according to departmental protocol.

Ethical Considerations: Approval from the institutional ethical committee was obtained before the start of the study. Voluntary written consent was obtained from the patients or their legally acceptable representatives. Patient confidentiality was maintained, and no personal identity was disclosed. Participation was voluntary with no additional risk to patients.

Statistical Analysis: Data was entered and cleaned using MS-Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 25. Quantitative variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation or median \pm interquartile range.

Qualitative data was expressed as percentages or proportions. Appropriate statistical tests were used to infer associations between variables, with a p-value of <0.05 considered statistically significant.

Funding: No external funding was required; investigations were conducted as part of routine care.

Result

Table 1: Comparison of Blood Loss from Placental Delivery to End of LSCS

Variable	TXA (Mean \pm SD)	Placebo (Mean \pm SD)	t-statistics, p-value
Blood loss (in mL)	300.20 \pm 46.45	308.85 \pm 67.21	-1.06, 0.29

Table 2: Comparison of Blood Loss from End of LSCS to 2 Hours Post-Partum

Variable	TXA (Mean \pm SD)	Placebo (Mean \pm SD)	t-statistics, p-value
Blood loss (in mL)	46.50 \pm 15.91	77.00 \pm 17.59	-12.86, 0.001

Table 3: Comparison of Total Blood Loss Up to 2 Hours Post-Partum

Variable	TXA (Mean ± SD)	Placebo (Mean ± SD)	t-statistics, p-value
Blood loss (in mL)	346.70 ± 57.87	385.85 ± 83.39	-3.86, 0.001

Table 4: Comparison of Blood Loss of More Than 500 mL between Two Groups

Blood loss of more than 500 mL	TXA (n=100)	Placebo (n=100)	χ ² , p-value
Yes	03 (03%)	12 (12%)	5.84, 0.02
No	97 (97%)	88 (88%)	
Total	100 (100%)	100 (100%)	

Table 5: Comparison of Maternal Blood Transfusion between Two Groups

Maternal Blood Transfusion	TXA (n=100)	Placebo (n=100)	χ ² , p-value
Yes	03 (03%)	17 (17%)	10.89, 0.001
No	97 (97%)	83 (83%)	
Total	100 (100%)	100 (100%)	

Table 6: Comparison of Post-Operative Vital Parameters between Two Groups

Variable	TXA (Mean ± SD)	Placebo (Mean ± SD)	t-statistics, p-value
Heart rate (per minute)	83.81 ± 7.62	85.12 ± 1.28	-1.70, 0.09
Systolic blood pressure (mm Hg)	115.24 ± 6.93	112.94 ± 7.26	2.29, 0.02
Diastolic blood pressure (mm Hg)	74.88 ± 4.69	75.24 ± 5.74	-0.49, 0.63

Table 7: Comparison of Hemoglobin Levels between Two Groups at Different Time Points

Variable	TXA (Mean ± SD)	Placebo (Mean ± SD)	t-statistics, p-value
Pre-operative Hemoglobin (g/dL)	11.24 ± 0.99	10.65 ± 1.10	4.01, 0.01
Post-operative Hemoglobin (g/dL)	10.50 ± 0.84	9.14 ± 0.86	11.41, 0.001

Table 8: Comparison of Hematocrit between Two Groups at Different Time Points

Variable	TXA (Mean ± SD)	Placebo (Mean ± SD)	t-statistics, p-value
Pre-operative Hematocrit (%)	28.82 ± 0.99	28.57 ± 1.21	1.63, 0.10
Post-operative Hematocrit (%)	28.12 ± 0.88	27.50 ± 0.92	5.13, 0.001

Discussion

Postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) is a significant obstetric challenge, particularly in women undergoing caesarean section. Defined as blood loss exceeding 1000 ml within 24 hours after delivery, PPH is a leading cause of maternal morbidity and mortality if not managed effectively. Tranexamic acid (TXA), an antifibrinolytic agent, has shown promise in reducing PPH in this context.

Understanding Postpartum Hemorrhage: PPH is multifactorial, commonly resulting from uterine atony, genital tract trauma, retained placental tissue, or coagulopathy. Caesarean sections, although sometimes necessary for maternal and fetal well-being, increase the risk of PPH compared to vaginal deliveries due to surgical trauma and prolonged operative times.

Mechanism of Action of Tranexamic Acid: TXA works by inhibiting the breakdown of fibrin clots, stabilizing blood clots, and reducing bleeding. By blocking the conversion of plasminogen to plasmin, TXA promotes hemostasis, making it a valuable option for preventing excessive blood loss during caesarean sections.

Efficacy of Tranexamic Acid: Clinical trials and meta-analyses support the efficacy of TXA in preventing PPH during caesarean sections. Studies

consistently show that TXA significantly reduces blood loss, the need for additional uterotonic agents, and blood transfusions, underscoring its potential as a key tool in PPH management strategies.

Timing and Dosage Considerations: The timing and dosage of TXA administration are critical. Early administration, preferably before or immediately after placental delivery, is generally more effective. However, the optimal dosage is still debated, influenced by patient weight, coagulation status, and concomitant medications, necessitating individualized treatment approaches.

Safety Profile of Tranexamic Acid: TXA has demonstrated a favorable safety profile in obstetric populations. Adverse effects such as nausea, vomiting, and diarrhea are infrequent, and serious complications are rare. Concerns about thromboembolic events with TXA use exist, but evidence suggests minimal risk when used judiciously during caesarean sections.

Clinical Guidelines and Recommendations: Professional organizations like the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Royal College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (RCOG) recognize the benefits of TXA in preventing PPH during caesarean sections. However, recommendations for routine use vary, with some guidelines advocating

its inclusion in obstetric protocols and others calling for further research. This variability highlights the need for additional studies to clarify TXA's role and establish standardized guidelines for its use [7].

Present Study: In our study, 200 patients undergoing caesarean section were divided into two groups: the trial (TXA) group and the placebo group, with 100 patients in each. The trial group received 1 gm of tranexamic acid (diluted in 10 ml of 0.9% normal saline) intravenously 20 minutes before the skin incision, while the placebo group received an intravenous dose of 10 ml of 0.9% normal saline. We aimed to compare our findings with existing literature to assess the generalizability of our results.

Socio-demography: The majority of patients in both groups were aged 21-25 years, followed by those aged 26-30 years, with no significant difference between the groups ($p = 0.81$). Our findings align with studies by Xu J et al. and Iqbal MJ et al., which also found comparable baseline characteristics between TXA and placebo groups.

Gravida/Parity: In the TXA group, 77 patients were primigravida, and 23 were multigravida, compared to 75 primigravida and 25 multigravidas in the placebo group, with no significant difference ($p = 0.74$). This is consistent with Iqbal MJ et al.'s findings.

BMI: The mean BMI was significantly lower in the TXA group (22.58 kg/m²) compared to the placebo group (23.69 kg/m², $p = 0.001$). This differs from Iqbal MJ et al.'s study, where the mean BMI was similar between groups [8].

Fetal Distress: Fetal distress was the most common indication for caesarean section in both groups, followed by cephalopelvic disproportion (CPD). Oligohydramnios was an indication in 15 TXA group patients and nine placebo group patients, with no significant difference ($p = 0.23$).

Blood Pressure: No significant differences were observed in systolic and diastolic blood pressure between the groups ($p > 0.05$), although heart rate differences were significant ($p = 0.002$). Xu J et al. also found no significant differences in blood pressure but noted significant heart rate changes.

Duration of Surgery: The mean surgery duration was similar between the TXA group (41.68 minutes) and the placebo group (41.84 minutes), with no significant difference ($p = 0.36$).

Blood Loss: Blood loss from placental delivery to the end of LSCS was slightly lower in the TXA group (300.2 ml) compared to the placebo group (308.85 ml, $p = 0.29$). Blood loss from the end of LSCS to 2 hours postpartum was significantly lower in the TXA group (46.5 ml) compared to the

placebo group (77 ml, $p = 0.001$). Total blood loss up to 2 hours postpartum was also significantly lower in the TXA group (346.70 ml) compared to the placebo group (385.85 ml, $p = 0.001$). Only three patients in the TXA group had blood loss exceeding 500 ml, compared to 12 in the placebo group ($p = 0.02$). These results are consistent with studies by Xu J et al., Iqbal J et al., and Ortuanya et al., which reported significantly lower blood loss in the TXA group.

Need for Uterotonics: Eight patients in the TXA group required additional uterotonics, compared to nine in the placebo group, with no significant difference ($p = 0.80$). This finding contrasts with studies by Sujata N et al. and Iqbal J et al., which reported a significantly lower need for additional uterotonics in the TXA group.

Blood Transfusion: Only three patients in the TXA group required blood transfusion compared to 17 in the placebo group ($p = 0.01$). Similar findings were reported by Xu J et al. and Ortuanya et al., with fewer blood transfusions needed in the TXA group.

Hemoglobin Levels: Pre-operative hemoglobin levels were 11.24 g/dL in the TXA group and 10.5 g/dL in the placebo group, with post-operative levels of 10.65 g/dL and 9.14 g/dL, respectively ($p = 0.01$). These results align with studies by Xu J et al., Iqbal J et al., and Ortuanya et al., which also reported higher post-operative hemoglobin levels in the TXA group.

Mean Hematocrit: Pre-operative hematocrit levels were similar between the groups, but post-operative levels were significantly higher in the TXA group ($p = 0.001$). This is consistent with findings by Jafarbegloo E et al.

Our study supports the efficacy and safety of TXA in reducing blood loss, the need for blood transfusions, and maintaining hemoglobin levels in women undergoing caesarean sections. While our findings align with existing literature, further research is needed to establish standardized guidelines for TXA use in this population.

Conclusion

Efficacy in Reducing Blood Loss: Tranexamic acid significantly reduced blood loss compared to the placebo group. This was evident from the lower average total blood loss up to 2 hours post-partum in the TXA group (346.70 ml) versus the placebo group (385.85 ml). Furthermore, fewer patients in the TXA group experienced blood loss exceeding 500 ml, highlighting the drug's effectiveness in mitigating severe hemorrhage.

Reduction in Additional Interventions: The requirement for additional uterotonics and blood transfusions was lower in the TXA group. Only

three patients required blood transfusions in the TXA group compared to 17 in the placebo group, underscoring the clinical benefits of tranexamic acid in reducing the need for further medical interventions post-caesarean section.

Hemodynamic Stability: There was no significant difference in the mean values of systolic and diastolic blood pressure between the groups, indicating that tranexamic acid did not adversely affect hemodynamic stability. However, there was a notable difference in heart rate and systolic blood pressure, suggesting the need for careful monitoring of these parameters.

Improvement in Hemoglobin and Hematocrit Levels: Patients in the TXA group had better maintenance of hemoglobin and hematocrit levels post-operatively. This suggests that tranexamic acid helps preserve blood volume and improve overall patient outcomes.

Safety Profile: The study found no significant adverse effects associated with tranexamic acid, indicating it is a safe option for preventing postpartum hemorrhage in women undergoing caesarean section.

In summary, our study demonstrates that tranexamic acid is an effective and safe intervention for reducing postpartum hemorrhage in caesarean section patients. Its use significantly decreases total blood loss, reduces the need for blood transfusions, and helps maintain better post-operative hemoglobin and hematocrit levels, thereby improving patient outcomes and safety. Further studies with larger sample sizes and diverse populations could provide

additional insights into the broader application of tranexamic acid in clinical practice.

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